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Studied on Heteropoly 6-Ammonium Molybdochromate

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THE synthesis and preliminary studies of 12-heteropoly molybdochromate have been reported by Mishra *et al.*¹. Kazanskii and co-workers² have synthesised some interesting hexamolybdochromate complexes. Older literature³ contains only a few report of molybdochromates without distinguishing the compounds to be true heteropoly complexes. The synthesis only of $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{[CrMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was reported⁴ in our previous communication but the details are discussed here. Ammonium molybdate (0.05M, 50 ml) together with glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and potassium dichromate solution (0.05M, 40 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr, evaporated to crystallization and left in atmosphere for several days. An orange coloured flaky powdery compound separated after 5 days. The compound was recrystallized thrice from hot water. Analysis of the compound was carried out by usual chemical and colorimetric methods. Chromium interferes⁵ with the estimation of molybdenum with α -benzoin oxime and hence had to be separated first. For this purpose molybdenum was quantitatively separated⁷ from the solution of the compound as molybdenum sulphide by passing H_2S at 5° at reduced pressure for 45 min in presence of formic acid and filtered. The chromium in the filtrate was estimated as lead chromate⁸. The precipitated molybdenum sulphide was dissolved⁷ in conc. HCl with minimum amount of KClO_3 , diluted, made alkaline and the molybdenum estimated with α -benzoin oxime. Molybdenum was also estimated colorimetrically by potassium thiocyanate method⁹. Nitrogen and hydrogen were estimated by element estimation technique. Analysis: Found: Cr, 4.02; Mo, 46.72; N, 6.62; H, 3.32. Calcd. for $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{[CrMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Cr, 4.22; Mo, 46.90; N, 6.68; H, 3.58%. The formulation of the compound was according to Evans¹⁰.

Thermoderivatographic studies: Clark¹¹ first made some thermal studies with a few heteropoly molybdates and tungstates. Heteropoly compounds, which can be regarded as condensation inorganic polymers¹², have further been studied by West and Audrith¹³ from their depolymerization point of view. The thermoderivatographic studies of the present compound show that 2 molecules of water are eliminated at 60° with an endothermic peak.

Another 2 molecules of water and 6 molecules of ammonia are eliminated at 160 and 250° with two successive endothermic peaks. No loss in weight was found upto a certain range of temperature. At 450° the remaining 6 molecules of water are eliminated with an exothermic peak clearly indicating complete break-down of the crystal lattice of the compound into the lower oxides of the constituent metals, which have been confirmed by analysis and ir spectra of the last product. Obviously these 6 molecules of water are acting as water of constitution of the compound. IR spectra of the compound ignited upto 260°, indicates complete removal of ammonia molecules in this stage, showing absence of bands at 1405 and 3100 cm^{-1} corresponding to N-H stretching and deformation frequency of NH_4^+ ion.

Infrared spectral studies: Tsigdinos¹⁴, Sharpless¹⁵ and Brown¹⁶ have examined infrared spectra of some of the heteropoly compounds. Infrared spectra of the prepared compound have been recorded from 4000 to 200 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer, model 577 grating infrared spectrophotometer. The spectrum is recorded in KBr pellets. The peaks are observed at 3190, 1525, 1405, 1090, 945, 900, 880, 740, 615, 510, 365, 245, 220, 200 cm^{-1} . The peak at 3190 (antisymmetric and symmetric O-H stretching modes¹⁷) is due to the presence of lattice water¹⁸. The peaks at 1405 and 1525 cm^{-1} can also be attributed to lattice water (H-O-H bending mode¹⁸). Recently Elsken and Robinson¹⁹ have shown that lattice water also absorbs at the lower frequency region (600-400 cm^{-1}) owing to librational modes. So, it may be considered that bands at 615, 510 cm^{-1} are due to the presence of lattice water in either of the three fundamental modes of free water molecules. The strong bands at 945, 900 and 740 cm^{-1} may be due to M-O and M-O-M linkage¹⁸ (M=Mo). The strong bands at 880 and 365 cm^{-1} are due to the tetragonal CrO_4^{2-} ions. The absorption at lower frequency region, 245, 220 or 200 cm^{-1} , may be attributed to the elongated stretching of compact M-O-M bridging of addenda atoms. The band at 1405 cm^{-1} corresponds to N-H stretching frequency²⁰. The broad band at around 3100 cm^{-1} corresponds to the deformation frequency of NH_4^+ ion²⁰.

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Metal Complexes of Sulfur-Nitrogen Chelating Agents: Organotin(IV) Derivatives of Diethylaminomethyl Ester of 2-Amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic Acid

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METHYL ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid is found to be a good chelating agent for several metal ions forming six-membered chelates¹⁻⁶. In view of antifungal properties^{1, 8, 7-11} of both the ester and the organotin(IV) compounds, it was considered interesting to synthesize organotin(IV) derivatives of another ester, diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid, $H_2NCCH_2CH_2CH_2CC(S)SCH_2N-$

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$(C_2H_5)_x(LH)_2$, and examine the structural features as well as the biological activities of these organotin(IV) complexes.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out under rigorous dry conditions. Solvents were dried by the standard techniques. Diethylaminomethyl ester

of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid was prepared by the literature method^{2, 12}. Monobutyltin trichloride (93°/10 mm), dibutyltin dichloride (153-156°/5 mm), tributyltin chloride (102°/0.5 mm), dimethyltin dichloride (185-190°/760 mm) and diphenyltin dichloride (93°/10 mm) were distilled before use. Dimethyltin(IV) diisopropoxide was prepared by the sodium isopropoxide method. Tin, sulfur and chlorine were estimated gravimetrically and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in benzene. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer as neat and nujol mull in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} . PMR spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

General method of preparation of the organotin(IV) complexes of diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid: Organotin(IV) chlorides (Bu_xSnCl_{4-x} , Bu_3SnCl_2 , Bu_2SnCl_2 and Ph_2SnCl_2), diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid and triethylamine (in appropriate molar ratios) were taken in THF (~60 ml) and the contents stirred at room temperature (~32°). Triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered out and the solvent removed *in vacuo*. The products (Table 1, Sl. No. 1 and 4-8) were crystallized from benzene-hexane and dried at 50°/0.1 mm/1 hr.

Preparation of the dimethyltin(IV) complexes: Dimethyltin(IV) diisopropoxide and diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid taken in appropriate molar ratios in THF (~60 ml) were heated under reflux. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the products dried at 50°/0.1 mm/1 hr (Table 1, Sl. No. 2 and 3).

Results and Discussion

Tributyltin(IV), dibutyltin(IV), monobutyltin(IV) and diphenyltin(IV) derivatives [compounds (II-V)] of diethylamino-methyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid, (I), have been obtained by the reactions of the appropriate metal chlorides in the presence of triethylamine (Table 1, Sl. No. 4-8).

Since the dimethyltin(IV) analogue could not be obtained in pure state, corresponding diisopropoxide was used as the starting material. Dimethyltin(IV) isopropoxide reacted readily to give the desired product (Table 1, Sl. No. 2 and 3).

Organotin(IV) compounds synthesised are dark brown shining foamy crystalline solids except tributyltin(IV) and monobutyltin(IV) complexes which are brown distillable liquids. All compounds